
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 28

The CHIANTI proton rate files (psplups)

This document gives information about the inclusion of proton rate coefficients in CHIANTI, and it describes the format for the CHIANTI psplups file. Note that the shorthand “proton rates” is often used, but the data product discussed in this document is always the proton rate coefficient.

1 General information

The dominant process for exciting atomic levels in the CHIANTI models is electron collisions. For transitions between levels with a small energy separation (usually levels in the ground configurations), the proton excitation rate can be comparable to the electron excitation rate. This was first demonstrated for a coronal ion (Fe XIV) by Seaton (1964).

Proton rates were first added to version 4 of CHIANTI (Young et al. 2003). The data were stored in “psplups” files, which have the same format as the “splups” files for electrons. However, in version 9 the format of the electron files was updated to the “scups” format (see Technical Report No. 13), but the proton data remained in the “psplups” format.

2 Assessment procedure

Proton rate coefficients (units: $\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) are taken from the data source and written to a “.prot” file. These files are *not* distributed with CHIANTI. The proton rates are assessed with the burly_ups.pro IDL procedure. This scales the rate coefficients, and the user performs a spline fit (either 5-points or 9-points). As part of the fitting, the user chooses a transition type that determines the type of scaling. Usually, proton rates are fit as Type 6 (see Young et al. 2003), but sometimes Type 2 gives a better fit.

Once the fit is finalized, the spline fit is written to the psplups file, and it is this file that is distributed in CHIANTI.

3 Reading the proton rates into IDL (descale_all)

To obtain the proton rate coefficient from the psplups file, the IDL routine descale_all.pro is used. An example for Fe XIII is:

```
IDL> log_temp=findgen(11)/10.+5.7
IDL> temp=10.^log_temp
IDL> zion2filename,26,13,fname
IDL> read_splups,fname+'.psplups',protstr,ref,/prot
IDL> descale_all,temp,protstr,0,prate
IDL> plot,temp,prate,/xlog
```

The 0 in the call to descale_all tells the routine to process the first entry in the protstr data structure.

The structure returned by read_splups has the tags given in Table 1. The spline value array (SPL) always has 9 elements, even if it was a 5-point spline. Elements 6-9 in the latter case are set to -1.

Table 1. The tags for the IDL structure returned by read_splups.

Tag	Data	Type
LVL1	Lower level for transition	Integer*1
LVL2	Upper level for transition	Integer*1
T_TYPE	Transition type	Integer*1

GF	Always zero for proton rates	Float*1
DE	Transition energy (Ryd)	Float*1
C_UPS	Scaling parameter	Float*1
NSPL	No. of spline points (5 or 9)	Integer*1
SPL	Spline values	Float*9

4 Data columns for the psplups files

There are either 11 or 15 data columns, depending on if a 5 or 9-point spline was fit to the data, and each is described below. The format for the column is indicated by Fortran-style notation: *i7*, *a30*, etc.

Column 1 – lower level index *i3*

The index for the energetically lower level of the transition. See discussion in Appendix 2.

Column 2 – upper level index *i3*

The index for the energetically higher level of the transition. See discussion Appendix 2.

Column 3 – transition type *i3*

The scaling applied to the proton rates requires the specification of a transition type (a number between 1 and 6).

Column 4 – oscillator strength *e10.3*

For electron data, this column gives the oscillator strength for the transition, but for proton rates this is always zero.

Column 5 – transition energy *e10.3*

The energy for the transition in Rydbergs. This is always a positive value.

Column 6 – scaling parameter *e10.3*

A parameter that defines the scaling applied to the proton rates.

Columns 7 to 11 (or 15) – scaled proton rate coefficient values *e10.3*

Spline values for the fit to the scaled proton excitation rate coefficient. There will either be 5 columns or 9 depending on if a 5 or 9-point spline was used for the fitting. For Type 6 transitions, there will be negative values for the spline points since the logarithm of the rate coefficient is fit. For some Type 2 transitions there will be an unphysical negative value that was necessary to obtain a good spline fit. When the data are descaled (with `descale_all`), negative proton rate coefficients are set to zero.

Comments section

The comments section begins and ends with a line containing only “-1”. Use existing files as examples of the format.

Appendix

1 Update history

Ver. 1.0, 23-May-2023: first version.

2 Energy ordering of levels

Atomic physicists will provide excitation rate coefficients, and the energy level ordering will usually come from their own structure calculation. The energy level order used in CHIANTI may be different from this. An example from the helium isoelectronic sequence is as follows.

Zygelman & Dalgarno (1987, Phys. Rev. A) give rate coefficients for the $n=2$ levels of C VI, including the $^2P_{1/2}$ to $^2S_{1/2}$ excitation. In CHIANTI, however, level 2 is $^2S_{1/2}$ and level 3 is $^2P_{1/2}$. For the psplups file, the recommendation in this case is to put “3” in column 1 and “2” in column 2. The energy for the transition (column 5) is positive.

However, it does not actually matter where the level indices go. The software checks the levels’ energies (from the elvlc file) and determines which of the two is energetically lower. The rate coefficients are then assigned to the transition from the lower to the upper level, and the de-excitation rate coefficient is computed and assigned to the upper-to-lower transition. The transition energy (column 5) is a positive value, whatever order the level indices are given.

The data assessor should never try to compute the de-excitation rate coefficient and put it in the psplups file in the case where levels are inverted. In addition, the transition energy (column 5) should always be positive.

3 Format for the prot files

The proton rate coefficients from the original data source are stored in “.prot” files. These are not distributed with CHIANTI, as the data are fit with splines and distributed as “.psplups” files.

The first line in the .prot file contains an integer specifying the number of temperatures (nT) at which the rate coefficients are specified.

For each transition, the data are stored on two lines.

Line 1 format:

Column 1 – lower level index *i5*

Column 2 – upper level index *i5*

Column 3 – transition energy (Ryd) *f10*

Column 4 onwards – temperatures (K) *e10*

Line 2 format:

Column 1 – lower level index *i5*

Column 2 – upper level index *i5*

Column 3 – empty column, not read *f10*

Column 4 onwards – rate coefficients ($\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) *e10*

Comments section

The comments section begins with a '-1' on a single line, and ends with another '-1' on a single line. Otherwise the comments have a free text format.